

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Record of water mass age and meltwater fractions, Weddell Sea

Deliverable D1.12

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Cover sheet: Credits to Oliver Huhn (University of Bremen, Germany), map showing locations of noble gas and transient tracer observations in the southern Weddell Sea,, 2021. Colours of the dots correspond to the maximum glacial meltwater fraction at each location.

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History of changes

Version	Date	Description	Authors (A) & Reviewers (R)
1	3 June 2024	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	2 October 2024	<p>Revision after the 1st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) PANGAEA link to the data collected in 2021 has been added to the document in section 2.3. 2) Graphical information on the spatial distribution of the data has been added to section 3: The spatial distribution can be seen on the map on the front page. In the result part, we added some figures showing the data (helium, neon, CFC-12, SF6) and some of the derived variables as examples (meltwater fractions, CFC-12/SF6 ages). 3) A publication by Huhn has been also added as reference to the section 1 and to the list of references. <p>Delivery to the European Commission.</p>	<p>A: O. Huhn (AWI)</p> <p>R: C. Bearzotti (DMI)</p>

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1. Publishable summary

In this data set (Huhn et al., 2024) we present trace gas measurements and derived variables such as basal glacial meltwater (GMW) fractions and water mass ages from the RV POLARSTERN expedition PS124 in the southern Weddell Sea (see map on the front page) in austral summer 2021. The trace gases comprise the lighter noble gases, i.e., total helium (He) and the excess above solubility equilibrium ΔHe , the $3\text{He}/4\text{He}$ ratio reported as $\delta^3\text{He}$, total neon (Ne) and the excess ΔNe , and the deviation from the equilibrium He/Ne ratio $\Delta(\text{He}/\text{Ne})$, as well as the transient anthropogenic trace gases chlorofluorocarbon (CFC-12) and sulphur hexafluoride (SF6) concentrations. From these noble gases (He and Ne) we derived glacial meltwater fractions. From the transient tracers we computed SF6-concentration ages, CFC-12/SF6 ratio ages and TTD (Transit Time Distribution) mean ages. This dataset adds unique observations-based water mass information to the circumpolar observations synthesized in WP1, and will further contribute to the evaluation of the numerical modeling efforts carried out in this work package.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Noble gas measurements

Water samples were taken from the CTD/water bottle systems without contact to atmospheric air into 40 ml gas tight copper tubes, which are clamped off at both sides. In the IUP Bremen noble gas lab the samples were pre-processed with a UHV (ultra-high vacuum) gas extraction system. Sample gases are transferred via water vapor into a glass ampoule kept at liquid nitrogen temperature. For analysis of the noble gas isotopes the glass ampoules are connected to a fully automated UHV mass spectrometric system equipped with a two-stage cryogenic system, a quadrupole and a sector-field mass spectrometer. Regularly, the system is calibrated with atmospheric air standards (reproducibility < 0.2%). Measurement of line blanks and linearity are done as well. The performance of the Bremen facility is described in Sültenfuß et al. (2009).

Noble gas concentrations are reported in nmol/kg for He and Ne and are additionally converted into excess above solubility equilibrium ΔHe [%] and ΔNe [%] using the solubility function from Weiss, 1971; $\delta^3\text{He}$ is reported in ‰. The precision for He is 0.23%, 0.33% for Ne and 0.43% for $\delta^3\text{He}$ (based on 9 replicate measurements).

2.1.2 Transient tracer measurements

The CFC-12 and SF6 water samples from the CTD-bottle systems were stored in ~220 ml glass ampoules by avoiding contact to the atmosphere during the tapping by a dedicated tubing and rinsing procedure. After sampling, the ampoules are flame sealed after a headspace of pure nitrogen had been applied.

The determination of CFC-12 and SF6 concentrations in the IUP Bremen gas chromatography lab is accomplished by purge and trap (cryogenic trapping at -65°C) sample pre-treatment of a precise water volume of 140 ml followed by gas chromatographic separation on a capillary column and electron capture detection (ECD). After thermal desorption the released gases are separated on a pre-column of type Alumina Bond/CFC, 0.54 mm ID x 3m, and a main column of type Alumina BOND/CFC, 0.54 mm ID x 30 m. SF6 and CFC-12 are then detected on a micro-ECD.

The analytical system is calibrated frequently by analyzing different volumes of known standard gas concentrations. The loss of CFCs and SF6 into the headspace is considered by equilibration between liquid and gas phase under controlled conditions before the sealed ampoules are opened and the volume of the headspace was precisely measured. A more detailed description of the measurement system is given by Bulsiewicz et al. (1998).

CFC-12 concentrations are reported in pmol/kg and SF6 in fmol/kg, both reported on SIO98 scale (Prinn et al., 2000). The concentrations were also converted into partial pressure [ppt] using the solubility functions from Warner and Weiss, 1985, and Bullister et al., 2002. The precision of the measurements, based on the comparison of the replicate samples, is 1.3 % for CFC-12 and 2.5 % for SF6. The accuracy for CFC-12 is 2% and for SF6 is 4%, including errors of calibration, linearity, standard-gas, gas volumes for calibration, water volume, gas loss into the head-space, and calibration scale. The detection limit is 0.002 pmol/kg for CFC-12 and 0.04 fmol/kg for SF6.

2.1.3 Noble gas-based glacial meltwater fractions

Glacial meltwater fractions were derived using the method described in Huhn et al., 2021. From surface measurements we calculated mean surface water excess of 0.3 ± 0.6 % for He and 0.9 ± 0.8 % for Ne. We derived glacial meltwater from He (21) and Ne (23) individually. Due to other sources of He from crustal He and Ne from sea ice formation, we advise to use either He- or Ne-based glacial meltwater fractions, whichever is greater (25). The uncertainty of the meltwater fractions is on the order of 0.1%, including errors of the measurements and uncertainties of the mean He and Ne surface excess.

2.1.4 Transient tracer-based water mass ages

We computed three types of water mass ages. For all types we assumed a common and constant surface water saturation of 80% for both tracers. In a first order approach, we used the SF6 concentration (i.e., the partial pressure) and compared it to the atmospheric tracer history (data from Bullister (2015) up to 2013 for CFC-12 and SF6; afterwards from Dutton, Hall, Montzka, et al. (2022) and Dutton, Hall, Dlugokencky, et al. (2022) for CFC-12 and SF6, respectively), to compute a concentration age, assuming pipe-flow without any mixing. In a higher order approach, we computed a so-called ratio age by comparing the CFC-12/SF6 partial pressure ratio to the atmospheric tracer ratio history, assuming mixing with tracer free, i.e., old water. Finally, we used the Transit Time Distribution (TTD) method (e.g., Huhn et al., 2013) to derive a mean age, regarding one-dimensional advection and dispersion, with a constant advection/dispersion ratio (Peclet number $Pe = 1 = \text{constant}$).

2.1.5 Parameters

1. Station number
2. Cast number
3. Bottle Number
4. Pressure [dbar]
5. Potential temperature [°C]
6. Salinity
7. Latitude
8. Longitude
9. Helium total, He [nmol/kg]

10. Flag He
11. Helium excess above solubility equilibrium, ΔHe [%]
12. Flag He
13. Helium isotope ration $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$, $\delta^3\text{He}$ [%]
14. Flag $\delta^3\text{He}$
15. Neon total, Ne [nmol/kg]
16. Flag Ne
17. Neon excess above solubility equilibrium, ΔNe [%]
18. Flag Ne
19. deviation from equilibrium He/Ne ratio, $\Delta(\text{He}/\text{Ne})$ [%]
20. Flag $\Delta(\text{He}/\text{Ne})$
21. Glacial meltwater derived from He [%]
22. Flag He
23. Glacial meltwater derived from Ne [%]
24. Flag Ne
25. Glacial meltwater derived from He or Ne, whichever is smaller [%]
26. Flag He / Ne
27. CFC-12 [pmol/kg]
28. Flag CFC-12
29. pCFC-12 [ppt]
30. Flag CFC-12
31. SF6 [fmol/kg]
32. Flag SF6
33. pSF6 [ppt]
34. Flag SF6
35. SF6 concentration age [years]
36. Flag SF6
37. CFC-12/SF6 ratio age [years]
38. Flag CFC-12 / SF6
39. CFC-12 and SF6 based TTD mean age [years]
40. Flag CFC-12 / SF6

The flags mean: 2 = good measurement or value, 3 = doubtful measurement or value, 4 = bad measurement or value, 6 = mean of replicate measurement, 9 = no measurement or value

2.2 References

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2.3 Open Science

The data were submitted to PANGAEA on 21 May 2024 and they are available in open access via <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.971321>

Hydrographic data included here were taken from <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.961780>

3. Results

The tracer measurements as well as the derived variables are in line with previous observations and results from the Filchner region.

The helium (Fig. 1A) and neon (Fig. 1B) measurements from the Filchner Trough region follow the glacial meltwater mixing line between the oceanic background (0.3 % for He and 0.9 % for Ne) and pure basal meltwater (Fig 1C). Deviations from that mixing line, that would indicate additions of crustal He or rejection of Ne from sea ice formation, are small compared to previous observations.

Figure 1: (A) helium excess and (B) neon excess versus pressure. (C) shows helium and neon excess and the meltwater mixing line (magenta line). Only “good” data are shown.

The derived glacial meltwater fractions (Fig. 2) range between 0 % at the surface and up to 1 % in the glacial meltwater core at a depth of 400-600 m. Regarding these results one has to consider that the locations of the observations are a considerable distance (~200-300 km) away from the Filcher Ice Shelf calving front. Hence, the glacial meltwater is already diluted on its way from the ice shelf cavity towards the shelf break by ambient waters.

Figure 2: Glacial meltwater derived from neon (x-axis) and helium (y-axis), according to Figure 1 (A). Only “good” values are shown.

The observed partial pressure of CFC-12 (Fig. 3A) and SF6 (Fig. 3B) exhibit surface water saturation up to 80% on the shelf. The first-order and most simple approach of a SF6 concentration age (assuming pipe-flow

and no further mixing after the water has left the surface layer) shows a water mass age of zero to five years in the surface layer and increasing ages with depth up to 15 years on the shelf.

Figure 3: (A) CFC-12 and (B) SF6 partial pressure. (C) shows as an example the CFC-12/SF6 ratio age versus pressure. Only “good” data and values are shown.

The higher approach of a CFC-12/SF6 ratio age (assuming only mixing with “old” and tracer free water) only accounts for the “young” and tracer-bearing fraction and is, hence, the youngest age one can derive from transient tracers (Fig. 3C). The CFC-12/SF6 ratio age ranges from zero to two years in the surface layer and increases with depth to the years on the shelf.

The likely most realistic age is the TTD mean age (accounting for a simplified advection and dispersion). It integrates in an idealized way the entire tracer history of all components contributing to the observed water mass from their descent from the ocean surface somewhere to the point and time of observation. It shows ages between zero and seven years in the surface layer. The ages are increasing with depth to over 20 years on the shelf and over 50 years at the shelf break. Ages are further increasing to 280 years on the slope and in the deep Weddell Sea basin; these high ages are due to admixtures of old Circumpolar Deep Water (or its Weddell Sea equivalent, the Warm Deep Water). A slight decrease of the ages close to the bottom might be an indication for admixtures of more recently ventilated Weddell Sea Bottom Water.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica.

The derived variables (in particular, the noble gas-based calculations of glacial meltwater fractions) quantify the ocean-controlled freshwater delivery from the Filchner Ronne Ice shelf, the earth’s largest ice shelf by volume in the southern Weddell Sea and allows insights on the export and distribution of meltwater on the continental shelves.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models.

Basal melting in coupled ice sheet-ocean and ice sheet-climate models can be verified with the parameters included in this delivery (in particular, the Glacial meltwater fractions).

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet-climate models.

Recent freshwater input due to basal melting in coupled ice sheet-ocean and ice sheet-climate models can be verified with the parameters included in this delivery (in particular, the Glacial meltwater fractions).

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

Basal meltwater is a key source water mass for Antarctic Bottom Water formation on the Antarctic shelves. Variables included in this deliverable allow tracing its pathways (in particular, the Glacial meltwater fractions) and timescales of the transport (transient tracer based water ages) on the shelf and beyond.

O7: Deliver free and open data access and contribute to international assessments, climate model development, observing initiatives and policymakers.

These measurements and derived variables are free and open to use by the community, and will therefore contribute to improve our understanding on the Southern Ocean, the Antarctic shelf seas system and their interactions with the Antarctic ice sheet. The data can thereby contribute to international assessments, and provide direct input for future observing initiatives, and policy response to improved understanding of global sea level rise uncertainties and the associated impact for coastal protections.